

SEEDS

Summary of achievements

The launch of the TROPOMI instrument on board the Copernicus Sentinel-5 Precursor satellite back in October 2017 represented a game-changer with respect to atmospheric composition observations from space. The TROPOMI instrument provides unprecedented information with refined temporal resolution and a spatial resolution of 3,5x5km.

The SEEDS project, which ran from January 2021 to December 2023, aimed at identifying key domains in which satellite-based approaches could enhance existing methods or create new methods that could target both increased scientific robustness and address new policy areas. Six key areas were explored:

- estimation of anthropogenic emissions (NO_x, NH₃ and biomass burning);
- estimation of natural emissions (BVOCs);
- land surface modelling and data assimilation to describe the impacts of drought, heatwaves and vegetation on surface deposition; and
- novel data assimilation methods to prepare for new satellite geostationary air quality observations such as Sentinel-4, with increased temporal resolution,
- exploration of operational pathways to CAMS
- stakeholder engagement in the economic, industrial and agricultural sectors for increase uptake.

The central objective of SEEDS has been to inform and support the evolution of the Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service (CAMS) by providing a proof-of-concept for a new service using satellite data, with the goal to improve the quality of the existing Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service (CAMS) products and enable new products and methods for increased stakeholder uptake in the economic, industrial and agricultural sectors.

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Main achievements and Lessons learnt

The SEEDS project showcased TROPOMI's potential to enhance both spatial resolution and temporal accuracy. The project consortium has created 8 distinctive emission datasets and 10 distinct land surface and deposition datasets. They provide a proof of concept for the use of TROPOMI data for improving satellite-based emissions, while laying the groundwork for future use of Sentinel-4.

The datasets are available through the **SEEDS Data portal** that offers an interactive visualisation tool and an easy download method. Following a FAIR approach (i.e. meeting the principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability), the datasets will remain available on the data portal for continued exploration after project completion and could eventually be integrated into WEKEO and CAMS ADS.

Next we reflect on the main scientific achievements and the lessons learnt related to the 6 main objectives that SEEDS targeted to address.

www.seedsproject.eu/data

Zenodo community

Zenodo has now a community for SEEDS to share the key scientific results. This Zenodo community lists all the datasets created in the project with their unique DOI and official citation. All the related peer-reviewed publications linked to the project research accepted during and after the project lifetime can also be found in the community.

Check it out!

<https://zenodo.org/communities/seeds-eu-project/>

Top-down anthropogenic emissions for improved estimations

Objective 1 – Prove the capabilities of satellite-based emissions and enable the provision of improved temporal emission products complementing the existing emissions currently available in CAMS.

SEEDS has produced top-down anthropogenic emissions of nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), ammonia (NH₃) and biomass burning emissions based on satellite data from TROPOMI and CrIS instruments, delivering hourly, daily, and monthly anthropogenic emission estimates.

The results of the SEEDS project show that although the resolution for point sources remains coarse at the moment, results are comparable with current inventories. These results can therefore be interesting in areas with reduced in situ data.

Most interestingly, the satellite data allows to appreciate variations over time, verifying yearly variations and estimating monthly and weekly variations. This enables a more detailed analysis of biases linked to temporal variations of emissions.

Overall, the SEEDS project demonstrated high added-value of exchange between bottom-up and top-down emission experts to increase the accuracy of current emission inventories. Satellite-based emission products allow independent evaluation of emission data and can help identify inconsistencies, and provide extra temporal information.

Bottom-up and top-down biogenic emission estimates

Objective 2 – Produce new up-to-date emissions of biogenic organic compounds (BVOC) and soil emissions of nitrogen oxides (NO_x) making use of satellite data through inverse modelling approaches and through data assimilation in land-surface vegetation models.

SEEDS has produced new up-to-date emissions of biogenic organic compounds (BVOC) both bottom-up (using land-surface and chemical transport models) and top-down estimates (using TROPOMI HCHO data with the MAGRITTEv1.1 inversion system). The latter proved to be of high quality, where low noise in the dataset allowed to perform weekly inversions of HCHO for the first time, a major improvement compared to previous studies.

Additionally, top-down emissions allowed identifying gaps in the current bottom-up inventories. However, large differences remain between both methods, underlining the need for more intercomparison work to better understand potential errors.

In addition, the DECSO inversion system has been applied in SEEDS to identify soil emissions of nitrogen oxides (NO_x) for the first time, where comparison with bottom-up inventories revealed gaps in the current bottom-up inventories (Lin et al, 2023).

Overall, the SEEDS results show that the comparison between bottom-up and top-down emissions improve the quality of emission data. Two concepts used in SEEDS are retained for integration in CAMS: the potential of using a simplified chemistry scheme for the oxidation of isoprene (CAMEO project), and the coupling of land surface and vegetation data for biogenic emissions estimates (MEGAN model).

Improved Land surface data and deposition estimates

Objective 3 – Propose to add an off-line land surface data assimilation modelling system to the CAMS production chain, providing assimilated soil moisture and vegetation variables from satellite data and a consistently derived bottom-up BVOC emission inventory.

Comparisons between the SURFEX land surface model and TROPOMI data has provided new insights, such as added value of LAI integration for model consistency. The study established SURFEX as an excellent basis for simulating dry deposition over vegetation, which allows the representation of complex interactions and dynamics due to drought and heatwaves. Further analysis is still required to better understand the importance of these data to the wider community working on dry deposition.

SEEDS provided a proof-of-concept by employing coupled land surface vegetation modelling to forecast deposition velocities to showcase their potential for improving geographical patterns and rapid changes. CAMS has shown interest in integrating this method into the SURFEX model, and while the initially proposed offline approach from SEEDS is not suitable, the underlying concept is considered interesting and will be implemented in the CAMS production chain.

Improved data assimilation algorithm for air quality forecasts

Objective 4 – Develop an advanced data assimilation algorithm (4DEnVar) to improve air quality forecasts in the CAMS operational system as an open source code that will help prepare the way for better exploitation of the hourly data from Sentinel 4.

SEEDS has developed 4DEnVar, an open-source advanced data assimilation algorithm to improve air quality forecasts in the CAMS operational system. 4DEnVar is able to account for various types of model errors responsible for a significant part of the uncertainty in air quality predictions, and allows to reduce analyses and forecast biases. The algorithm is available for download from the SEEDS data portal.

SEEDS therefore provided algorithms to prepare for the use of Sentinel 4 geostationary satellite data, enabling the assimilation of highly resolved temporal variability of observations and accounting for the presence of multiple competing error terms. This was achieved through two distinct methods: the development of the 4EnVar algorithm for future application within the CAMS consortium, and the creation of a new branch of DECSO capable of deriving hourly emissions.

Pathways to operationalization of SEEDS methods in CAMS

Objective 5 – Demonstrate the capabilities of enhanced uptake of EO observations by testing its new products in the current CAMS regional production chain.

Initially, the integration of SEEDS products in CAMS was expected to showcase enhanced forecast quality scores. Due to the unavailability of timely data to be included in the forecast chains in time, experiments were focused on hindcasts and analysis. However, demonstrating score improvements in hindcast and analysis mode is challenging, as the assimilation of observations has a more significant influence in the final scores than changes/improvements in the underlying chemical transport models and their inputs. In retrospect, the design of experiments should have focused on the forecast data chain and taken stock of the added value of the improved temporal variability derived from satellite-based products.

CAMS has acknowledged the capabilities of SEEDS products, methods, and approaches, with two distinct paths proposed for operationalization. First, SEEDS top-down emissions can complement the evaluation of existing bottom-up inventories by providing insights into temporal changes, missing sources, and total emissions, even if they don't directly improve statistical scores. They will eventually be part of real-time emissions for forecasting. Secondly, SEEDS provided a proof of concept on the use of coupled land surface vegetation modelling to derive bottom-up BVOCs emissions and deposition velocities forecasts.

Identification of the added-value and innovation pathways

Objective 6 – Engage stakeholders from industrial, agricultural and urban environmental management sectors to secure the added value of the SEEDS emission and deposition products and to identify innovation pathways towards further user uptake.

The stakeholder engagement activities involved stakeholders from various sectors such as industry, agriculture, and urban environmental management. Stakeholders working on bottom-up inventories, as well as city planners and environmental authorities, showed particular interest in SEEDS' top-down emission data, and discussions provided interesting insights regarding the steps required for making these products useful for the community. Engaging agricultural stakeholders and large industrial emitters proved more challenging.

The availability of the data portal from the second year proved highly beneficial, enabling a more fruitful engagement with stakeholders from multiple groups. The experience in SEEDS highlighted the importance of delivering readily accessible data to enable innovation pathways. The presence of value creators was identified as a critical factor in the adoption of these methods by users.

Final remarks

SEEDS has been an inspiring project and I am very thankful to have been working with such a competent and creative team to prove the capabilities of satellite-based approaches to improve emissions and depositions of the nitrogen cycle.

The main added value of SEEDS is the impressive amount of data now available for benchmarking and evaluation in our data portal. It includes an unprecedented amount of consistent satellite-based emission and information spanning over 4 years with daily, weekly and monthly resolution. They provide a proof of concept for the use of TROPOMI data for improving satellite-based emissions, while laying the groundwork for future use of Sentinel-4. SEEDS has also provided algorithms to prepare for the use of Sentinel 4 geostationary satellite data, through the development of the 4EnVar algorithm and the creation of a new branch of the inverse modelling system DECSO capable of deriving hourly emissions.

The SEEDS top-down emission data is currently used by emission experts across Europe, both within CAMS and in the Task Force for Emission Inventories and Projections. I am happy to see that the outreach work carried out in SEEDS has helped promote closer cooperation between the bottom-up and top-down emission communities. It has shown that there are complementarities and added-value in the comparison of both emission estimation approaches and that the identification of inconsistencies can lead to improvements of the emission estimates. SEEDS has shown that satellite-based emissions can provide valuable insights into the temporal variability of emissions and help identify missing sources (such as NO_x soil emissions).

Leonor Tarrason
SEEDS project coordinator

The communication and collaboration with the CAMS community has been very rewarding all through the project. SEEDS concepts have been retained for CAMS product evolution, in particular concerning the potential of using a simplified chemistry scheme for the oxidation of isoprene and the coupling of land surface and vegetation data for biogenic emissions estimates. SEEDS has provided a proof of concept on the use of coupled land surface vegetation modelling to derive biogenic emissions and forecast deposition velocities improving geographical patterns and rapid changes.

Even if it was difficult for us to show during the extent of the project that SEEDS products could directly improve CAMS statistical scores, the approaches tested in the project open a way for the eventual incorporation of coupled land-surface-vegetation modelling and real-time top-down emissions in the CAMS forecasting chain.

Further cooperation with the CAMS community and value creators and end users in the industrial, agricultural and biodiversity sectors will be necessary to contribute to the provision of timely and accurate information on the state of the environment to help us deal with the current triple planetary crisis concerning the impacts on our climate, biodiversity and natural environment.